

Abrasive Water Jet Machining of Carbon Epoxy Composite

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Abstract:

Carbon epoxy composite is an extremely strong and light weight carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) material. It is widely used in naval, aerospace, transportation, and structural applications. Traditional machining of carbon epoxy composite material is difficult due to excessive tool wear, excessive stresses and heat generation, delamination, high surface waviness etc. Abrasive water jet machining (AWJM) is viable option for machining carbon epoxy composite due to its certain advantages like no heat and thermal distortion, low cutting forces, no tool wear etc. The present paper describes the research work involved in experimental study of AWJM of carbon epoxy composite. Influence of four process parameters of AWJM namely water pressure, traverse rate, stand-off distance and abrasive mass flow rate on surface roughness and kerf taper of machined samples is studied. It is found that water pressure and traverse rate are most significant parameters to control surface roughness and kerf taper. Surface roughness and kerf taper decreases with increase in water pressure (Figure 1) and decrease in traverse rate. Further, the defects including delamination, fiber pull out and abrasive embedment in AWJ machined carbon epoxy composite are also investigated. Scanning electron microscope is used to examine defects in machined samples. Maximum delamination length is considered as response for analysis of variance to investigate the influence of process parameters on delamination. It is found that abrasive mass flow rate and traverse rate are most significant process parameters followed by pressure. Delamination decreases with increase in water pressure and abrasive mass flow rate; and decrease in traverse rate and stand-off distance.

The findings of present study are certainly useful in process planning and to develop strategy for selection of optimum process parameters for defect free and accurate machining of carbon epoxy composite by AWJM.

Keywords:

Fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP), carbon epoxy composite, abrasive water jet machining, process parameters, water pressure, traverse rate, surface roughness, kerf taper, defects, delamination.

Figure 1: Effect of water pressure on surface roughness

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MORPHOLOGY OF BINDER-JET ADDITIVE MANUFACTURED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Abstract:

Binder-jet 3D printing is one of the additive manufacturing (AM) techniques employ in fabrication of intricate parts, by utilizing metal powders. Many implementations of AM exist from areas as diverse as food industry to biomedical engineering; such a broad spectrum usage of this technology makes it extremely attractive when combined with its low cost, reliability, color range, and complexity abilities. (Fidan, Elliott, Cossette, Singer, Tackett, 2018). In this work, a method of making metal matrix composite was adopted which involves printing metal samples from gas atomized powder and infiltrating a lower melting metal into the porous sites of the sample.

In order to achieve this, gas atomized structural amorphous metal (SAM) alloy powder was used for Binder-jet 3D printing of the base samples, while Bronze pellet were utilized for unpressurised liquid metal infiltration because of its lower melting temperature and high ductility.

The SAM alloy powder was first characterized by Morphologi G3. The samples obtained were characterized by scanning electron microscopy, electron dispersive x-ray as well as micro indentation. Liquid metal infiltration of bronze into binder-jet printed structural amorphous metal resulted in a fully dense net-shape parts. Electron dispersive spectroscopy results show that the bronze filled out the pores as expected. Micro-indentation results show variation of hardness across the metal matrix as the SAM alloy sections exhibit higher hardness than the bronze sections. Generally, it was found that infiltration of bronze into structural amorphous metal improved homogeneity of the material and makes the samples denser.

Keywords:

Amorphous metal, binder jet printing, infiltration, Porosity, density

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Identification and quantification of cobalt in the copper-cobaltifier oxidized ores of the Congolese copper belt: application of mineralogical reconstitution to optimize leaching efficiency

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Abstract:

Cobalt is a very important metal for the development of the current industry due to its multiple uses including the manufacture of rechargeable batteries for use in electric cars and smartphones (Sadegh et al., 2010, Palisade research, 2016). The DRC is currently the world's leading producer of cobalt (USGS, 2016). In 2017, it supplied 82,461 tonnes of Co, which represents 63% or more than half of global production (CTCPM, 2017). But when we look at the current processes in the DRC to produce cobalt, we can see that in the leaching stage, the yield hardly exceeds 80%. In other words, 20%, or more than 16,000 tonnes of Co for the year 2017 have been evacuated in leaching rejection.

When it comes to optimizing the recovery of metals in conventional metallurgy, it is common practice to proceed with leaching tests in the laboratory by optimizing the various parameters that influence the performance: pH, stirring speed, temperature, granulometry, etc. This way of proceeding does not justify the limitation of the metallurgical performances. In this study, the mineralogical reconstitution was implemented to identify and quantify the cobalt contained in samples of the copper-cobaltifier oxidized ores of the Congolese copperbelt.

Thus, the methodology adopted consisted in coupling the mineralogical study with the metallurgical study in order to highlight the leachability of the different cobalt bearing minerals. The chemical analyzes (elementary and mineralogical) were performed by Atomic Emission Spectrometry, Diffraction and Fluorescence of X-rays and Electron Scanning Microscopy. The mineralogical distribution of cobalt (cobalt department) in the different phases was calculated using the QEMSCAN automated mineralogy system. The leaching tests were carried out in a reducing acid medium.

The results obtained showed that cobalt is found in useful minerals which are heterogenite, asbolane and malachite; and in gangue minerals consisting of Fe oxides, chlorite and clays. Heterogenite and malachite leach well: up to 98% and 75% respectively. Fe oxides and chlorite leach poorly: up to 47% and 21% respectively. The overall leaching yield is therefore limited by the kinetics of leaching of the gangue minerals which are relatively refractory. In order to improve this yield, two tracks have proved promising: the reduction of the pH up to a value of 0.8 and the heat pretreatment at 600 ° C. Very low pH leaching increases yield by 10% and thermal pretreatment improves ore porosity and dehydroxylation of heterogenite (Tshipeng, 2018).

Keywords:

Identification and quantification of cobalt, copper-cobaltifier oxidized ores, Congolese copperbelt, mineralogical reconstitution, leaching efficiency.

Study of the Phase Transformation behavior of low dimension Structure of MnO₂

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Abstract:

Control the dimension of materials must affect the phase space or appear a series of novel performances such as electricity, photology and magnetism. In this work, we prepared low dimension(1D, 2D) MnO₂ nanostructure contained several phase(α , β , δ) to study the phase transformation under heat treatment to raise the service temperature of materials in high temperature field. For 1D MnO₂, the δ -MnO₂ performed phase transformation while the other phase lost lattice oxygen directly during the whole heat treatment process. Unexpectedly, the 2D δ -MnO₂ is more stable than 1D δ -MnO₂ and the phase transformation has been delayed clearly. Moreover, the new α crystal phase which transformed from 2D δ -MnO₂ has more out-standing thermal stability compared with α -MnO₂ prepared directly, it also more stable than the phase which transformed from 1D δ -MnO₂(Fig.1). This distinctive phenomenon is attribute to the ultrathin 2D MnO₂ layer structure can undertake a part of energy from high temperature surroundings(Fig.2). Define the mechanism of phase transition and stability of two-dimensional materials are benefits to synthesis of composite materials with different phases and enhance stability of functional materials in future

Keywords:

2D MnO₂ nanosheets, layered structure, thermal stability, phase transformation

Figure 1: The XRD of (a) 1D α -MnO₂, (b) 1D β -MnO₂, (c) 1D δ -MnO₂ heat treats at different temperature; (d) 2D δ -MnO₂ heat treats at low temperature and (e) at high temperature.

Figure 2: The schematic of 2D δ -MnO₂ phase transition mechanism. Step 1: 2D δ -MnO₂ loss interbedded H₂O molecules; Step 2: layers folded adhere to K⁺ ions at 400°C; Step 3: folded layers formed 2×2 tunnel structure perfectly over 450°C. The illustration intermediately is MnO₆ octahedral units. Red sphere is oxygen atom, the rest of blue spheres are manganese atoms.

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Structural, Optical and Thermoluminescence study of MnO doped Lithium Borosilicate glasses

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Abstract:

MnO doped lithium borosilicate glasses of the composition $50\text{B}_2\text{O}_3\text{-}30\text{SiO}_2\text{-(}20\text{-x)Li}_2\text{O-xMnO}$ (where $x = 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.0\text{mol}\%$) were synthesized by melt quenching method. Structural and optical properties of these glasses were investigated using UV-Vis reflectance spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopic techniques. The samples were exposed to γ -ray dose of 100Gy and 1kGy respectively and their thermoluminescence spectra (TL) was recorded upto maximum temperature of 400 °C. The glow curve showed single broad peak in the temperature range 100 – 150 °C and the composition with 0.5 mol% MnO has the optimum response. The variation of kinetic parameters with the increasing concentration of the dopants was studied and all the glass samples exhibited second order kinetics. The mechanism of decrease in the TL output with the gradual increase in MnO content is explained upon the basis of existence of different valence states of Mn ions in the glass system.

Keywords:

Borosilicate glasses; XRD; FTIR; Optical band gap; Thermoluminescence

Figure 1: A proposed TL mechanisms with Mn³⁺ ions in Li₂O-B₂O₃-SiO₂ glasses.

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Magnetic Semiconducting Quantum Dots: Advanced Material for Future Technology

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Abstract:

Magnetic ion doped semiconducting quantum dots (SQDs) have potential applications in spin based electronic devices. Therefore, it is important to study these materials from fundamental and technological viewpoints. Quantum confinement effects are known to enhance exchange interactions and induce magnetic properties that were previously not observed in bulk materials. In fact, properties are known to alter dramatically when dimensions are reduced to nanometer size regime. Magnetic ion doped-SQDs are an advanced class of material with the potential to generate easily controllable spin polarized currents for spintronic devices. Because the magnetic exchange interactions (between carriers and magnetic ions or between magnetic ions and magnetic ions) determine to a large extent the optical, and magnetic properties of the DMSQDs, how to manipulate the exchange interactions and has become a key issue. In this view I briefly discuss on synthesis and investigations of transition metal (Cr and Fe) doped CdSe and ZnSe QDs. Ultra small Cr-doped CdSe magnetic QDs are exhibited room temperature ferromagnetism, as expected from theoretical arguments. Surprisingly, a low temperature phase transition is observed at 20 K that is believed to reflect the onset of long range ordering of the single domains. Cr doped ZnSe QDs showed CdCr₂Se₄ spinel inclusion in ZnSe QDs with anti-ferromagnetic interaction. Fe (4.6%) CdSe quantum dots (5.1 nm) exhibited super paramagnetic behavior with a blocking temperature of ~90 K and have an evidence of ferrimagnetisms. Fe (1, 5 and 10 %) doped ZnSe quantum dots (1.8 nm) showed super paramagnetic to spin-glass behavior with magnetic interactions.

Biocompatibility of CdSe/V₂O₅ core/shell QDs was carried out at normal conditions and exhibited a noticeable enhance in viability of cell lines for CdSe/V₂O₅ core/shell QDs. Surface modification of CdSe QDs with V₂O₅ shell has increased the biocompatibility due to V₂O₅ shell formation prevents free Cd ions to diffuse into the cells from the surface of CdSe QDs. These interesting properties impact a new paradigm from diluted magnetic semiconductor dots and core/shell QDs for highly suitable applications in spintronics, memory storage, cellular imaging, drug delivery, photovoltaics (PV) and infrared (IR) devices.

Keywords:

Quantum dots, nanometer, transition metal, exchange interaction, spinel inclusion, ferromagnetism, anti-ferromagnetic, biocompatibility, core/shell, spintronics, memory storage, cellular imaging, drug delivery, photovoltaics

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Adsorption and corrosion green inhibition properties of Omega-3 on mild steel in 1 M HCl: Experimental and theoretical studies

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Abstract:

The addition of inhibitors can effectively protect metals from corrosion. Lately, it has become a widely used method in materials corrosion and protection [1–2]. Organic inhibitors will chemically adsorb onto a metal surface through heteroatoms (N, O, S, P), double/triple bonds or aromatic rings [3–4].

An expired pharmaceutical product, Omega-3, was studied as save drug to prevent mild steel (MS) corrosion in 1.0 HCl by using weight loss, potentiodynamic polarization, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and DFT modulation technique. The inhibition efficiency in-creased with increasing drug dose and decreased with increasing temperature, reaching a max-imum value of 99% at 298K and 10⁻³ M. Polarization data showed that the drug is of a mixed type. The inhibition of MS corrosion by Omega-3 can be attributed to the adsorption ability of drug molecules onto the reactive sites of the MS surface. The adsorption process follows the Langmuir isotherm via physical adsorption(fig1).

Results showed that the correlation between experimental (inhibition efficiency, ΔG_{ads}) and quantum calculation parameters (dipole moment, EHOMO, ELUMO). It was concluded that the high corrosion inhibition efficiency of Omega-3 was associated with its strong adsorption as a barrier film on the mild steel surface.

Keywords:

Mild steel; Electrochemistry; Weight loss; Inhibitor; Theoretical; Omega-3.

Figure 1: Langmuir plot for Omega-3 inhibitor on mild steel in 1 M HCl.

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Material Characterization at Nano order length scale – A SAXS study

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Abstract:

Characterization of materials is an integral part of research work to understand all about its properties with reference to the nano order structure if any in particular. Narrowed down to nano order length scale not only resolving the atomic level properties associated with the materials but also opens the window to visualize the more details in it to understand well about the material properties. Scientists explore various advanced techniques to resolve the structures at nano order length using powerful synchrotron radiation facilities available across the Globe. Although such facilities are rare for common scientific community still they resolve the structure with the facilities readily available low powered x-ray radiation generators and one such study has been explored by the innovative powerful tool named Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS). This presentation reflects the importance of SAXS study in structural characterization of the materials at nano order length scale.

A Prospective Study of Thermal and Mechanical Characteristics of Ceramic particulate filled polyester composites

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Abstract:

This research deals with the processing and characterization of spherical boron nitride particulate filled polyester composite and its hybrid. With improved conduction capability and minimal weight, the spherical particulate boron nitride filled polyester composite and its hybrid composites can be used for applications such as engine casings, military equipments aviation industry etc. that needs better and faster heat transfer as well as heat dissipation. The effect of embedment of BN on the thermal and mechanical characteristics like effective thermal conductivity (k_{eff}), glass transition temperature, co-efficient of thermal expansion, tensile strength and hardness are studied. This work uses FEM as a very good predictive tool for the assessment of thermal conductivity of composites. The proposed theoretical correlations too can serve as very good empirical models for spherical inclusions to estimate k_{eff} for composites within the percolation limit. With enhanced thermal conductivity, improved transition temperature, reduced co-efficient of thermal expansion, the polyester composites with appropriate proportions of boron nitride and the hybrid containing boron nitride and peanut husk particulates which are not susceptible to moisture absorption and tend to enhance the strength can be used for various kinds of applications like heat engines, fins and heat sinks, printed circuit board substrates etc. where faster heat transfer is a necessity.

Keywords:

Polymer composites, Thermal conductivity, Ceramic composites, Polyester, Boron Nitride, Hybrid composites

Figure 1: Graph illustrating the comparison of k_{eff} values obtained from different models with experimental values for single filler composite

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A quarter of a century after its synthesis and with >200 papers based on its use, 'Co(CO₃)_{0.5}(OH)·0.11H₂O' proves to be Co₆(CO₃)₂(OH)₈·H₂O from synchrotron powder diffraction data

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Abstract:

The successful attempt to solve the crystal structure of 'Co(CO₃)_{0.5}(OH)·0.11H₂O' (denoted CCH), based on synchrotron powder diffraction data, leads to a drastic revision of the chemical formula to Co₆(CO₃)₂(OH)₈·H₂O [hexacobalt(II) bis(carbonate) octahydroxide monohydrate] and to a hexagonal cell instead of the orthorhombic cell suggested previously¹ [Porta et al. (1992). J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans. 88, 311–319]. Here, the post synthesis heat treatment process was deliberately avoided to utilize the hydrated part (associated with lattice water). Surprisingly, it not only resulted in a new type of crystal structure but also exhibited the excellent electrochemical energy storage performance. The synthesized material has malachite type structure connected by infinite chains of [CoO₆] octahedra, sharing edges along a short c-axis, with space group P6₂m, interconnected by CO₃²⁻ groups and delimiting tunnels having a three branched star section. These tunnels play a significant role in determining the charge storage properties by cationic diffusion from the interior of the crystalline framework.² All reports discussing cobalt hydroxycarbonates (CCH) without any structural knowledge and especially its topotactic decomposition into Co₃O₄ have, as a result, to be reconsidered. The morphological and structural results indicate the nanowires growth along (001) direction.

Keywords:

Cobalt(II) carbonate hydroxide hydrate; powder diffraction; ab initio; synchrotron; malachite.

Figure 1: Unit cell projection of the Co₆(CO₃)₂(OH)₈·H₂O structure along the short c axis, showing the rings of nine [CoO₆] octahedra connected either by edges or faces (three of them are empty, i.e. half of the Co₂ atoms in blue, avoiding face sharing), forming tunnels along c-axis.

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Novel anticancer nanodelivery system based on protocatechuic acid functionalized graphene oxide

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Abstract:

Advances in nanotechnology, enabling the synthesis of new nanomaterials, have led to the development of a number of new drug delivery systems. These drug nanocarriers have the potential to enhance the therapeutic efficacy of a drug, since they can be engineered to modulate the release and the stability and to prolong the circulation time of a drug, protecting it from degradation. Graphene oxide with two-dimensional aromatic surface is an ideal substrate for adsorption of anticancer drugs with aromatic rings by π - π stacking interactions and its large surface area. [1-3] Here, a promising and novel nanocarrier, synthesized graphene oxide (GO) by improved Hummer's method was employed to load an anticancer agent, protocatechuic acid (PA), for efficient PA delivery. The PA loading in the designed anticancer nanocomposite (PAGO) was estimated using UV-Vis instrument, to be 12.6% and drug release from nanocomposite at 7.4 and 4.8 phosphate-buffered solution (PBS) was pH sensitive and in sustained manner. The FTIR, Raman and X-ray diffraction (Figure 1) results were further confirmed successful conjugation of protocatechuic acid with graphene oxide via hydrogen bonding and π - π interaction. The PAGO nanocomposite inhibits the growth of cancer cell lines without affecting normal fibroblast (3T3) cells.

Figure 1: Figure shows powder X-ray diffraction patterns of graphite, graphene oxide nanocarrier, PAGO nanocomposite and protocatechuic acid. The formation of GO is confirmed with the considerable shift of (002) characteristic diffraction of graphite to lower angle, which is assigned to the diffraction of the (001) for the graphene oxide (Figure 1B). The expansion in the interlayer distance of consecutive carbon basal planes in GO could be due to the intercalated water and incorporation of various oxygen functional groups such as hydroxyl, epoxy, and carboxyl in the carbon layer structure (Figure 2B). The XRD pattern of PAGO nanocomposite (Figure 2C) reveals an increment in the basal spacing due to the PA loading onto GO nanocarrier under alkaline condition, as reflected by the observation of peak at lower 2θ . The absence of PA phase (Figure 2D) from XRD curve of PAGO nanocomposite (Figure 2C) further proves successful loading of PA onto GO nanosheets and formation of nanocomposite.

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Effects of Simulation Parameters on Residual Stresses for High Energy Electron Beam

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Abstract:

By using simulation method, we proposed an applicable procedure of High Energy Electron Beam (HEEB) using Rhodotron accelerator (TT200) with power of 100 MeV and discussed various parameters, such as Stability Limit, Dynamic Yield Stress, Peak Pressure, Pressure Pulse Duration, HEEB Spot Size, and Multiple HEEB. The effects of parameters related to the simulation method of the HEEB process on the residual stresses of 7075 Aluminum alloy at Electron Energy of 10 MeV with different doses 80, 90, 100, and 110 KGy are discussed. Parametric sensitivity analyses were performed to establish the optimum processing variables of the HEEB process. In addition, we evaluated the effects of initial residual stress. The agreement of the final results remained well within the expected acceptable range

Keywords:

Simulation; Residual Stresses; High Energy Electron Beam

Development facile and rapid enzyme-free optical sensor using amino-group borane@ZnO Nps system for L-lactate detection in food products

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Abstract:

L-lactate is conjugate base of α -hydroxy acid (AHA), key organic chemical in biology, food and chemical industries, etc. We are reporting first time, the facile and rapid non-enzymatic sensor for L-lactate detection in milk sample using boronate added zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs), synthesized by aqueous solution method. XRD confirmed the wurtzite structure of ZnONPs with avg. crystallite size=20 nm. SEM micrographs indicate nearly spherical like structure formation of pure ZnO NPs. UV-VIS measurements revealed, the absorption edge is found to be blue shifted (230–372nm) which could be attributed to the confinement effects. The FT-IR spectrum sharp peaks in the 466 to 690 cm^{-1} range attributed to the vibrational phonon of ZnO NPs. The 100 μL of ZnO Nps (0.5mg/ml) added with aminogroup borane (10 mmol/L) at ambient conditions in the presence of polar protic solvent (1000 μL) medium used for the optical sensor development. The UV-VIS spectrometry study revealed that, with the increase of L-lactate spiking (5-100 mM) in commercial Nestle lactogen (1-infant formula powder milk 5gm/lt) sample showed an absorption peak increase from 0.8 a.u (5mM at $\lambda=295$ nm) to 1.25 a.u (100mM at $\lambda=288$ nm) response time is 1–2 min (Figure 1). This is expected due to ZnO NPs enhancing the binding and redox reaction mechanism between aminogroup borane and L-Lactate. The calibration graph resulted the lower detection limits (LOD) of 3 mM in this studied milk sample. The authors are reporting first time this non-enzymatic optical nanosensor. Further, colorimetric sensor development for various industrial applications are under progress

Keywords:

L-lactate, aminogroup borane, Zinc oxide, milk, optical sensors, food products.

Figure 1: Detection of L-lactate in commercial milk sample by ZnO Nps (0.5mg/ml) added with amino-group borane (10 mmol/L) at ambient conditions in the presence of polar protic solvent (1000 μL) medium. L-lactate content was also validated by standard enzymatic kit assay (Megazyme).

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An Investigation into the Impact of Daylight on Perceived Color of Façade: Understanding the Role of Chromaticness

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Abstract:

Color selection has always been a classic problem in exterior color design for the simple reason that façade color is commonly chosen at the architect's office, regardless of different external conditions affecting color perception. This issue often leads to an apparent discrepancy between the selected color and the perceived color of façade. So far, extensive research has been carried out to identify, classify, and study the influence of these conditions on perceived color. However, little attention has been paid to the importance of color attributes. Hence, this article attempts to grasp better the significance of chromaticness, as briefly discussed in earlier studies, in the variation pattern of perceived color while daylight condition differs. In order to determine perceived color, each test subject was asked to compare the color seen on the façade to the standard color samples of natural color system index and choose the matching one, using a designed color-measuring device. The results obtained from 93 participants demonstrate 3 things: First, they further support the belief that perceived color is influenced in both hue and nuance under varied daylight circumstances. Second, they confirm previous findings that indicated chromaticness would affect the extent of color shifts. And above all, a comparison of the results reveals that façade colors of higher chromaticness values have had less shifts in hue, yet greater shifts in whiteness. Finally, the findings suggest that chromaticness together with the external conditions, under which the color is to be seen, should be carefully considered when selecting the façade color.

Keywords:

Chromaticness, color perception, daylight, exterior color design, perceived color.

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Novel magnetic Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles impregnated Bentonite based colorimetric sensor for Aflatoxin B1 detection in corn and commercial foods

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Abstract:

Rapid detection of aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) in corn and commercial Kellogg's Corn flakes spiked samples using magnetite Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (FeNps) as well as impregnated with bentonite clay (Fe-Bt) is reported. Characterization studies were performed with FeNps and the Fe-Bt composites to optimize the detection of AFB1 by colorimetric sensor. XRD peak at $2\theta = 35.54$ (311, inverse cubic spinel phase structure), $2\theta = 26.59$ (210) in Fe Nps and Fe-Bt composite respectively. Particle size of nearly 12 nm (Fe Nps) and 35 nm (Fe-Bt) was calculated. The FTIR characteristic peak between 700-503 cm^{-1} corresponds to Fe-O stretching; Si-O and Si-O-Al shift in impregnated clay. The FeNps and Fe-Bt is initially magnetised by inducing magnetic field, $B=500\text{Gauss}/1\text{hr}$. Each 0.25mL of FeNps and Fe-Bt (0.5mg/ml) added with curcumin dye (0.5 ml of 1mg/ml) in alkaline medium at $\text{pH}=9.51$ is added with AFB1 in methanol at ambient conditions are loaded for colorimetric studies. With the increase of AFB1 (0-4 ppb) in corn flour, the UV-VIS absorbance peak intensity study showed a shift for FeNps from $\lambda=489\text{nm}$ (0ppb) to 432 (4ppb) and Fe-Bt, $\lambda=492\text{nm}$ (0ppb) to 438 (4ppb). The standard calibration graph resulted the limit of detection, LOD= 0.57 ppb (FeNps) and 0.8 ppb (Fe-Bt) with corn. This sensing mechanism may be due to the electron transfer from dye LUMO to nanoparticles CB and involved in $\pi-\pi^*$ transition. Further, the lowest LOD in FeNps is explained due to strong magnetization and the effective electrostatic binding of phenolate anions in AFB1 with the oxidized curcumin. Results were validated with HPLC. This selective and rapid method can be alternate to existing high cost and tedious methods

Keywords:

Bentonte, nanocomposite, colorimetric, phenolate anions, aflatoxin, corn.

Figure 1: Figure illustrates the schematic reaction of curcumin enol form (X2) with Fe (A1) and Fe-B (B1) to give oxidized curcumin red complex (A2 and B2). Further opened lactone moiety of AFB1 (Y1) give phenolate anions (Y2) which react with oxidized curcumin to give yellow complex (A3) and orange complex (B3)

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Disclosure of the Hydrogen Generation and Accumulation in Steel and Graphite Irradiated in Inert Environment

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Abstract:

In traditional power engineering hydrogen may be one of the first primary source of equipment damage. This problem has high actuality for both nuclear and thermonuclear power engineering. Study of radiation hydrogen embrittlement of the steel raises the question concerning the unknown source of hydrogen in reactors. Later unexpectedly high hydrogen concentrations were detected in irradiated graphite. So alloying of steel and graphite by hydrogen in nuclear reactor takes place.

It is necessary to look for this source of hydrogen especially because hydro-gen flakes were detected in reactor vessels of Belgian NPPs.

As a possible initial hypothesis about the enigmatical source of hydrogen one can propose protons generation during beta decay of free neutrons inasmuch as protons detected by researches at nuclear reactors as witness of beta decay of free neutrons.

Keywords:

Nuclear reactor, steel, graphite, source of hydrogen

A New Ultra-Lightweight Composite Proppant for Hydraulic Fracturing

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Abstract:

The results of a study on experimental characterization of a new Chemically Modified and Reinforced Composite Proppant (CMRCP), which derived from renewable resources is presented. For characterization purpose, Microscopic Characterization (FESEM, SEM and EDX) is used to investigate the microstructure and the elements of the CMRCP, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) for conformational analysis of organic, inorganic and polymeric materials, and Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) to determine the range of temperature degradation. Other characteristics envisaged are roundness and sphericity, specific gravity, bulk density, turbidity, crush resistance and fracture conductivity. The tolerable pressure (8,000 psia) and temperature (300 °F) of CMRCP play a key role when placed in the fracture. The low specific gravity, high values of roundness and sphericity, low bulk density, low acid solubility, high crush resistance, and low turbidity have been resulted from the CMRCP. The results of physical tests are compared with other proppants and fracture conductivity is compared to the commonly known walnut-hull proppant (i.e., ULW-1.25). The developed CMRCP shows promising results and meet the established API/ISO standards. These results are of key importance for the consequent development of lightweight high-strength composite proppants.

Effect of silver doping on the structure and properties of Fe-MWCNT composites

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Abstract:

In the present work attempt is made to study the structural aspects of silver doped iron-MWCNT composites of varying concentration of MWCNT under optimized processing conditions during ball milling and spark plasma sintering; further, effort is exerted to understand the role of silver doping in influencing the structure and properties of Fe-MWCNT composites. The iron powder with various weight percent of MWCNTs (1, 2, 3 and 4wt %) are milled by utilizing a high energy planetary ball mill; 0.1wt. % silver has been used in each composite mixture. The mechanically milled silver doped Fe-MWCNTs composite powders were consolidated by spark plasma sintering. The sintering temperature was kept at 7000C with applied pressure, 60 MPa.

X-ray diffraction study is done to analyze the constituent phases in Fe-MWCNT nanocomposite powder. Microstructural study is carried out by optical and field emission scanning electron microscope. Transmission electron microscope is used for microstructural study at high resolution. Vibrating Sample Magnetometer is used to study the magnetic property of the composites. Fourier transform infrared spectrometer is used to characterize the different bonds present in the experimental composites. Moreover, Raman spectroscopy was carried out to study the structural integrity of MWCNT in the composite. The DC electrical conductivity of Fe-MWCNT nanocomposites pellets are measured using two probe method. It is found that silver doping in iron-MWCNT composites can conserve the structure of MWCNT quite well. In a silver doped composite there is no contamination at the interface of MWCNT and iron crystals. Further observation verifies that high energy ball milling leads to flatterring of the matrix on which MWCNTs are firmly embedded. Silver protects the MWCNT from chemical damage. High energy ball milling followed by Spark Plasma Sintering does not form any chemical synthesis product. Conductivity of iron increases remarkably in silver doped composite and in silver doped iron-4 wt. % MWCNT composite a conductivity value higher than that of aluminum is achievable. It is further observed that the saturation magnetization of silver doped Fe-MWCNT composite increases by 25% over that of pure iron at 3wt. %MWCNTs. Silver atoms tether the surface of MWCNT and act as a coating over the MWCNT. This form of functionalization is responsible for excellent interfacial bonding and improves the physical properties of nanocomposite quite significantly.

Size-Induced Metal-Insulator Transition in Metal Nanoparticles

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Abstract:

Nanoscale particles are indeed fascinating and have been well known as a predictive intermediary model in defining the atomic, molecular and the bulk states of matter. In physical chemistry, it is accepted that the small metal particles' properties found to be strikingly dependent on the change of particle size with a similar chemical composition of the particles. Of these properties, the ultimate cessation of metallic conduction within a single small particle drives this overwhelming importance phenomenon; so-called Size Induced Metal Insulator Transition (SIMIT). This most outstanding characteristic owes the well-defined answer to the groundbreaking of the size dependent question in such a case that the small metal transform from itinerant to localized electron system. Many serious attempts have been made to closely interwoven the agreement between the ramifications of 'Gedanken theory' and experiment and as a result; they rather suffer from the inadequacy of rationalizing measurement. Therefore, the possibility of a non-destructive method to probe the Size Induced Metal Insulator Transition in small colloidal particles of silver (Ag) exists. For a small Ag particle limited, the optimized conditions should be less than the magnetic skin depth, δ where the electric dipole absorption come to the fore with the effective conductivity, is expressed as when brought into a fixed frequency of microwave electric field. The conductivity is indeed dependence on the metal particles sizes.

Keywords:

Size-Induced-Metal-Insulator Transition, metal nanoparticles, colloidal particles, conductivity, microwave electric field.

Figure 1: The HR-TEM images of Ag nanoparticles with mean diameter, $d_m \sim 60 \pm 5$ nm.

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Graphene: Novel Nano Approach for Remarkable Corrosion Resistance

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Abstract:

Corrosion and its mitigation costs dearly (any developed economy loses 3-4% of GDP due to corrosion, which translates to ~\$250b to annual loss USA). In spite of traditional approaches of corrosion mitigation (e.g., use of corrosion resistance alloys such as stainless steels and coatings), loss of infrastructure due to corrosion continues to be a vexing problem. So, it is technologically as well as commercially attractive to explore disruptive approaches for durable corrosion resistance.

Graphene has triggered unprecedented research excitement for its exceptional characteristics. The most relevant properties of graphene as corrosion resistance barrier are its remarkable chemical inertness and impermeability and toughness, i.e., the requirements of an ideal surface barrier coating for corrosion resistance. However, the extent of corrosion resistance has been found to vary considerably in different studies. The author's group has demonstrated an ultra-thin graphene coating to improve corrosion resistance of copper by two orders of magnitude in an aggressive chloride solution (similar to sea-water). In contrast, other reports suggest the graphene coating to actually enhance corrosion rate of copper, particularly during extended exposures. Authors group has investigated the reasons for such contrast in corrosion resistance due to graphene coating as reported by different researchers. On the basis of the findings, author's group has succeeded in demonstration of durable corrosion resistance as result of development of suitable graphene coating. The presentation will also assess the challenges in developing corrosion resistant graphene coating on most common engineering alloys, such as mild steel, and presents results demonstrating circumvention of these challenges

Biography

Professor Raman Singh's primary research interests are in the relationship of Nano-/microstructure and Environment-assisted degradation and fracture of metallic and composite materials, and Nanotechnology for Advanced Mitigation of such Degradations. He has also worked extensively on use of advanced materials (e.g., graphene) for corrosion mitigation, stress corrosion cracking, and corrosion and corrosion-mitigation of magnesium alloys (including for the use of magnesium alloys for aerospace, defence and bioimplant applications). His professional distinctions and recognitions include: Editor two books, one on NDT of Corrosion and other on cracking of welds, Editor-in-Chief of a journal, member the Editorial Boards of a few journals, leader/chairperson of a few international conferences and regular plenary/keynote lectures at international conferences, over 210 peer-reviewed international journal publications, 15 book chapters/books and over 100 reviewed conference publications, and several competitive research grants (that includes 4 Discovery, 7 Linkage and one ITRH grants of Australian Research Council). Prof Singh has supervised 40 PhD students. His vibrant research group at Monash University comprises of PhD students from different disciplines (Mechanical, Chemical, Materials and Mining Engineering, and Science) as well as from different cultural backgrounds (Australian, Middle-eastern, Chinese, Malaysian, Indian, American and Israeli).

Fabrication and characterization of nanofibrous polyacrylic acid superabsorbent using electroblowing technique

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Abstract:

Most commercially available hydrogels have a low specific surface area due to the spherical or pseudo-spherical geometry, which highly affects the swelling properties of the hydrogels. In this study, a nanofibrous superabsorbent were prepared using gas-assisted electrospinning (also known as electroblowing) of Poly(acrylic acid) (PAA). The morphology of the nanofibrous hydrogel and its effect on the swelling performance were investigated. For this purpose, different concentrations of PAA solutions, operating conditions for the gas-assisted electrospinning technique, as well as cross-linking agents (poly(ethylene glycol), glycerol, and 1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether) were studied. Moreover, sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was used to neutralize the PAA solutions in different contents. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy was used to investigate the hydrogel structure and the chemical cross-linking reaction. The scanning electron microscopy was used to investigate the fibers morphology. Free absorption, absorption under load, and the rheological behavior of the specimens were investigated, demonstrating that the specimen prepared using 9 wt% PAA, 30 wt% was neutralized by 50 wt% NaOH solution, electrospun at 20 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and cross-linked by 1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether had the highest swelling ratio.

Keywords:

Hydrogel; Superabsorbent; Poly(acrylic acid) (PAA); Gas-assisted electrospinning.

A Novel Microwave Energy-Based Approach to Nanostructured Fullerene-Like Metal Chalcogenides' Preparation

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Abstract:

Metal Chalcogenides (MCs) have emerged as an extremely important class of nanomaterials with applications ranging from lubrication to energy storage devices. Here, the discovery of a universal, ultrafast, energy efficient, and facile approach, to prepare MC nanostructures by using microwave (MW) energy, is reported. A suitable combination of precursor chemicals was selected for reactions that took place on polypyrrole nanofibers (PPy NFs) in MW energy medium. PPy NFs serve as the conducting medium to absorb MW energy to provide the heat for precursor chemicals to get separated into their metal and chalcogenide constituents. The MCs are formed as nanoparticles (NPs) which eventually undergo a size dependent, multi-stage aggregation process to yield different kinds of MC nanostructures. Most importantly, this is a one step MC formation process that is much faster and much more energy efficient than all the other existing methods and can be universally employed to produce different kinds of nano-MCs (e.g., MoS₂, and WS₂), as well.

Keywords:

Carbonization, conducting polymer, metal chalcogenide, microwave energy.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the experimental procedure.

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Development of high dense Aluminium based nano-composite devices for its application as solar collector

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Abstract:

In this research work, a novel approach has been applied with respect to powder metallurgy route for the development of Aluminium (Al) based composite materials for the fabrication of devices to be used as solar collector for domestic and industrial use. The applied technology has been executed to synthesize Aluminium-Graphene composite materials using high energy ball milling process followed by vacuum sintering to get the required devices. The fabricated devices and synthesize composite materials at later stage have been evaluated in terms of different micro-structural characterization tools like FE-SEM, EDAX, EPMA etc for qualitative and quantitative analysis, which shows well distribution of the constituents of Al-Graphene composite materials over the scan areas. The physical property of the sintered samples has also been evaluated through density measurement and it is found to be $\approx 97\%$ density after sintering. The thermal fusing of Al based materials at the optimum temperature of sintering is found to be satisfactory with required strength and the sintered Al based devices are found to be of improved thermal conductivity taken into reference the pure Al sintered one, as a result of which it can be well deployed as a solar thermal collector for solar water heating.

Keywords:

Nano-composites, powder metallurgy, high energy ball milling, Sintering, FE-SEM, EDAX, EPMA, density, thermal conductivity, solar collector, solar water heating

Figure 1: Figure illustrating Al based composite material to be used as Solar Thermal Collector for Solar Water Heating

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Morphological Investigation of N-((4-Benzhydryl piperazin-1-yl) methyl) Nicotinamide as inhibitor for Brass Corrosion in acidic chloride solution

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Abstract:

The inhibition effect of N-((4-Benzhydryl piperazin-1-yl) methyl) Nicotinamide (BMN) on brass in 1 M HCl was studied using weight loss, potentiodynamic polarization, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and Cyclic voltammetry (CV) methods. To elaborate the mechanism of corrosion, thermodynamic parameters such as free energy, entropy and enthalpy were calculated. BMN has significant inhibition efficiency on brass in 1 M HCl over the temperature ranges from 30 °C to 60 °C. Polarization measurements indicate that BMN acts a mixed type corrosion inhibitor. AC impedance indicates that Rct value of BMN increase with increase in the concentration. CV reveals that the addition of inhibitor controls the oxidation of the copper on the brass metal. The structure of BMN was characterized by the spectral studies like FT-IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR. The surface morphology of brass on BMN was analyzed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The structure of BMN was distorted to quantum chemical indices using density functional theory (DFT) which imply that the inhibition efficiency of BMN was very much related to the quantum parameters

Keywords:

Mannich base, Brass, Acid corrosion, EIS, CV, DFT.

Figure 1: Represents the CV for brass in 1 M HCl in the absence and presence BMN at 30 °C

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